

BIO-MEDICAL IMAGE COMPRESSION AND ENHANCEMENT OF LOW CONTRAST IMAGES

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Abstract:

when the usage of computers become more and more enormous amount of data is produced but handling these bulky data is so challenging because storing and transforming these raw data in all perspectives is not so easy, it requires high computational resources often cause high cost and this is the considerable issue in on growing world. Therefore, efficient way of storing and transforming huge amount of data demands the need of image compression using various compression techniques which is available in the market today. All compression techniques come under either lossy or lossless type where as in lossy, the compression ratio is good but distortion is added while in lossless the compression ratio is poor but distortion is not added, quality also good and both are suitable for specific applications. Such technique is discrete cosine transformation [DCT], discrete wavelet transformation [DWT] are widely used as transformation techniques in many industry standards. Doing compression for ordinary images and medical images is entirely different because in bio medical field, medical images contains useful and more important information which is used for diagnosis and must be regain at the decoding stage otherwise it causes clinically wrong diagnosis. In this paper we show how DCT, DWT and hybrid transformation is work with ordinary image and medical image using post filtering technique. It shows compression ratio before and after and contrast is enhanced by using various techniques Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE), Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE).

Keywords: DCT, DWT, HYBRID, CLAHE, AHE

1. INTRODUCTION

As a part of digital world today where most of the data is generated in digital form, and it needs digital image processing concept for image interpretation and analysis. In digital image processing image is to be processed in different steps using various techniques and methods with the help of mathematics. In digital image processing the most important methods are compression and enhancement on images. In modern world huge amount of digital data in the form of images and videos are often generated. To store and transmit these bulky data in multimedia would requires high computational resources like bandwidth and challenging task also. Now image compression comes into picture and plays a very crucial role in efficient storage and transmission of digital images. Image compression can be achieved by removing unwanted and redundant information in the image. Basic redundancies are spatial, spectral and psycho visual redundancies needs to be deleted as part of compression. Image compression generally falls in two types' lossy compression and lossless compression. In lossy compression the reconstructed image after decompression is not exactly same as original image and it introduce artefacts due to degradation after compression moreover it achieves high compression ratio but not suitable for medical field. While in lossless compression the reconstructed image after decompression is exactly same as original image and it does not

produce any artefacts at the degradation step. Compression ratio is low compare to lossy and best suitable for medical field. Here one noticeable key issue is compression of ordinary image is significantly different than compression of medical image. There are many transformation techniques are available today under both lossy and lossless compression. The most widely used popular techniques in lossy are DCT [Discrete cosine transformation] [1] and DWT [Discrete wavelet transformation]. Both having pros and cons and suitable for specific applications. Hybrid transformations are using to encash the advantages of both. As of today tremendous work has been taken on this issue to get better compression ratio and good quality images and seen how hybrid works well for huge amount of data and how it suits for medical images [12] in bio medical field compared to ordinary images.

2. TRANSFORMATION TECHNIQUES FOR MEDICAL IMAGES

2.1 Discrete Cosine Transformation [DCT]:

DCT is one of the popular widely used transformation technique in many industry standards for image compression. It was developed by Ahmed, Natarajan, and Rao in 1970's and which is very close to discrete Fourier transform (DFT). DCT is mainly used to mapping an image signal into a frequency component and it is popular for its energy compaction. It separates the image signal into different frequencies like low energy or frequency and high energy or frequency. In reality the human eye is more perceive to low frequency components compare to high frequency components. According to this less important information is discarded using **quantization** process and more important information is retained and retrieved while decompressing using Inverse Discrete Cosine Transform (IDCT). Unfortunately, some distortion is added while re constructing the image, due to this **post filtering technique** is recommended for removing distortion and to have good visualize. DCT come up with many types 1-Dimensional DCT, 2-Dimensional DCT and 3- Dimensional DCT, but in our implementation we have consider 2-Dimensional DCT.

Implementation:

Steps for implementing image compression using DCT as shown in fig:

1. Divide the input image into 8*8 blocks of pixels according to $N*N$ where $N=8$.
2. Apply 2D DCT on each and every block in all angles.
3. Perform quantization on each block to discard less energy occupied, so actual compression starts here.
4. Encode the data using coding standard.

Image re construction using image de compression.

1. Decode the data using coding standard.
2. Post filtering is performed to remove blocking artefacts which is produced at compression stage.
3. De quantization is performed while reconstructing the image.
4. Inverse DCT is performed.
5. Compressed image is produced.

Fig 2.1: Steps in DCT Implementation

2.2 Mathematical support for implementing DCT algorithm.

The DCT Equation for computing each pixel P(x, y) in the input image has given below.

The DCT equation (Eq. 1) computes the i,j^{th} entry of the DCT of an image.

$$D(i,j) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2N}} C(i)C(j) \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \sum_{y=0}^{N-1} p(x,y) \cos\left[\frac{(2x+1)i\pi}{2N}\right] \cos\left[\frac{(2y+1)j\pi}{2N}\right] \quad 1$$

$$C(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \text{if } u = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } u > 0 \end{cases} \quad 2$$

Suppose if we use JPEG compression, the standard is 8*8 where N = 8, which modifies the above equation and shows below.

$$D(i,j) = \frac{1}{4} C(i)C(j) \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^7 p(x,y) \cos\left[\frac{(2x+1)i\pi}{16}\right] \cos\left[\frac{(2y+1)j\pi}{16}\right] \quad 3$$

For computing above in scalar representation is so difficult when compare to vector computation so equation for vector representation as shown below.

$$T_{ij} = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \cos\left[\frac{(2j+1)i\pi}{2N}\right] & \text{if } i > 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad 4$$

Now compute DCT by using matrix multiplication $D=TMT^T$ where T is the DCT matrix and M is the image block.

2.3 Discrete Wavelet Transformation [DWT]:

Discrete wavelet transformation [2] is popular for its inherent multiresolution nature on the basis of wavelet [11]. In DWT the whole image is represented as some set of wavelet functions. Input data can be represented as detailed coefficients or high level coefficients and approximated coefficients or low level coefficients. These data can pass through two kinds of filters low pass filters and high pass filters, after that approximated coefficients retained and pass to next stage. There are different dimensions with DWT, 1-D DWT, 2-D DWT etc. In this paper we considered 2-D DWT for getting better result.

2.4 Hybrid Transformation [DCT+DWT]:

When we go with standalone DCT and DWT, both having advantages and disadvantages. To exploit the advantages in both use hybrid transformation using DCT and DWT [10]. Hybrid transformation [3] performs by applying discrete cosine transformation on discrete wavelet transformation. Basically DWT is partitioning the original image into low frequency and high frequency components, identify only the low frequency components and apply DCT on it to get high compression ratio so that we encash the advantages of both.

3. ENHANCEMENT OF LOW CONTRAST IMAGES

Due to some adverse conditions noise may be added at the time of capturing, even after compression the image may get distorted and contrast will become low, finally all these may affect the image quality. This will force us to go with image enhancement. Many enhancement techniques are available today to improve visual quality by increasing their contrast. Contrast enhancement plays very important role especially in medical imaging field while analyzing images by experts, radiologist and doctors. The enhancement techniques for increasing image contrast are falls in two categories spatial domain and frequency domain. We concentrate on spatial domain techniques, examples are histogram equalization (HE) [9], adaptive histogram equalization (AHE), contrast adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) and hybrid histogram equalization (HHE) etc.

Basically contrast enhancement can be done by using two different methods, global enhancement and local enhancement [8] respectively. In global enhancement it considers the entire image for enhancement but small areas will get neglected and it is the drawback also, where as in local enhancement individual small areas is to be considered and it is more effective than global. Histogram equalization is of type global enhancement, so to make more effective in our paper we implemented two local contrast enhancement methods are adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) [6] and contrast adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) [5].

3.1 Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE):

It is a type of local contrast. Here transformation is applied on sub images rather the whole image therefore different histograms [4] needs to be calculated instead single histogram. Later it uses some techniques to operate on sub images and to assemble. However, AHE takes long computation time, addition of noise, and generates unnatural appearance of images.

3.2 Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE):

It is improved version of adaptive histogram equalization [7]. Basically it is developed to enhance low contrast bio medical image with natural appearance. This methods partitioning the original image into non-overlapping contextual areas. Two parameters namely clip limit and window size is used to control the overall performance of contrast enhanced. With respect to brightness, the value of clip limit should be zero whereas by decreasing the window size will increase the contrast.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Image compression is performed on a sample X-ray image using various transformation techniques like DCT, DWT hybrid transformation techniques and also low contrast X-ray image is enhanced using various enhancement techniques like HE, AHE and CLAHE. The selected sample X-ray image and its corresponding histograms are show in various figures. While comparing, hybrid transformation gives better result over standalone DCT or DWT at the same time CLAHE has given better quality in terms of PSNR over AHE.

Bio medical image:

x-rays.jpg 45.5KB

Uploaded Image. Height=390 Width=390

compression ratio: 0.6571 original size: 46.552kb final_size:15.965kb

Fig 4.1: uncompressed image

Fig 4.2: compressed image

The above figure 4.1 and 4.2 are mathematically measured as shown below.

If n_1 and n_2 denote original image before compression and output image after compression respectively, the relative data redundancy R_D of the original image n_1 can be defined as

$$R_D = 1 - 1/C_R \quad \text{eq-1}$$

Where C_R represents compression ratio is defined as, $C_R = n_1/n_2$.

$C_R = 46.552/15.96$ (from figure 1 and 2)

$$C_R = 2.916 \quad \text{eq-2}$$

$$R_D = 1 - 1/2.916 \quad R_D = 0.65$$

For the case $n_2 = n_1$ and $R_D = 0$, implies there is no redundant data in n_1 . If n_2 is less than n_1 where $C_R \rightarrow \infty$ and

$R_D > 1$, indicating that there is a significant compression and redundant data is high. If n_2 greater than n_1 where

$C_R \rightarrow 0$ and $R_D \rightarrow -\infty$, implying that n_2 contains much more data than the n_1 original image. Usually, $C_R = 10(10:1)$ defines that n_1 set has 10 data carrying units for every 1 unit in the n_2 or output image. Therefore, corresponding redundancy R_D of 0.6 means 60 percent of the data in n_1 is redundant with respect to the n_2 output or processed image.

NON-MEDICAL IMAGE:

Analysis given for ordinary or no-medical image as shown below in fig 4.3

Relative data redundancy for non-bio medical image is calculated as shown below.

$$R_D = 1 - 1/C_R \quad \text{referred eq-1}$$

Where C_R represents compression ratio is defined as, $C_R = n_1/n_2$.

$C_R = 2864.498/195.14$ (from figure 3)

$$C_R = 14.67 \quad \text{referred eq-2}$$

$$R_D = 1 - 1/14.67$$

$$R_D = 0.9$$

Fig 4.3: compression ratio of non-medical image before and after

compression ratio: 0.9319 original size: 2864.498kb final_size:195.14kb

RD of 0.9 means 90 percent of the data in n1 is redundant with respect to the n2 output or processed image in non-bio medical image.

Image compression using DCT and DWT are shown below. It shows hybrid compression is always better than standalone compression techniques.

Fig 4.4: original image

Fig 4.5: after DCT

Fig 4.6: after DWT

Fig 4.7: after Hybrid

HISTOGRAMS of various contrast enhancement techniques given below.

Fig 4.8: histogram of (a) original (b) CLAHE (c) AHE

Fig 4.9: shows the AHE enhance the contrast of X RAY image.

Fig 4.10: shows the CLAHE enhance the contrast of X RAY image.

It has seen from the above figures CLAHE enhanced better than AHE than others.

5. CONCLUSION:

In bio medical field the improper visualized images may cause clinically wrong diagnosis by the various medical experts, at the same time uncompressed data (images) can be medically expensive. To resolve the above issues efficient transformation techniques are needed. In our paper we implemented by using DCT, DWT and Hybrid DCT+DWT, results showed hybrid transformation has given better compression ratio over standalone DCT or DWT. After image compression, data may be not suitable for proper visualization because of noise amplification, to make proper local contrast enhancement techniques AHE and CLAHE are used here, results showed AHE better than global enhancement and CLAHE gives better results over AHE.

Future enhancement: Even after CLAHE enhancement is very difficult to differentiate foreground and background regions of the image because it equally enhances both foreground and background. In future it will overcome by using adaptive entropy index histogram equalization (AEIHE).

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7. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This research paper is a completely original work of its authors; it has not been published before and will not be sent to other publications until the PRIA Editorial Board decides not to accept it for publication.

Conflict of Interest

The process of writing and the content of the research paper do not give grounds for raising the issue of a conflict of interest.

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